

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20977894

Farmers' Perception And Adoption Of Climate Smart Agricultural Practices On Sorghum Production In Northwestern Nigeria

*Umar Ibrahim; Abdullahi Abubakar Khidir; Tijjani Abu Rimi & Sani Ibrahim

Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development,
Faculty of Agriculture,
Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: 08035703790; email: iumarknk@gmail.com
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9582-5982>

ABSTRACT

This study analyzed farmers' perception and of adoption of climate-smart agricultural (CSA) practices for sorghum production in Northwestern Nigeria. A total of 334 sorghum farmers were sampled using a multi-stage sampling technique. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires and administered by trained enumerators. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Kendall's coefficient of concordance. The results of the socio-economic characteristics revealed that the mean age of sorghum farmers was 41 years, with 87.5% being male and 91.0% married. Most respondents had household sizes of 6–11 persons (42.0%) and farming experience ranging from 4 to 21 years (58.3%). Qur'anic education was the highest level of education attained by 34.7% of farmers, while 78.0% reported fewer than two extension visits annually. The study identified several CSA practices available and adopted in the study area, including timely planting, use of improved sorghum varieties, crop rotation, mixed cropping, and appropriate fertilizer application, while adoption of practices such as mulching, soil and water conservation, agroforestry, and climate information services was relatively low. Farmers' perception of CSA practices showed a fair level of agreement, with a Kendall's coefficient of concordance of 0.36, indicating moderate consensus among respondents regarding the benefits of CSA in improving yield, soil fertility, and resilience to climate variability. The study concluded that sorghum farmers had positive perceptions of CSA practices and moderate adoption of CSA practices. It was recommended that extension services be strengthened, farmer training on CSA practices be intensified, and access to affordable inputs, credit facilities, and reliable climate information be improved to enhance CSA adoption and sorghum productivity in Northwestern Nigeria.

Keywords: Farmers, Perception, Adoption, Sorghum, Knowledge, Status, CSA Practices

INTRODUCTION

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) is a versatile and climate-resilient crop that belongs to the grass family (*Poaceae*). It is a vital food, feed, and biofuel crop globally, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. Sorghum originated in Africa over 5,000 years ago and was later introduced to Asia, America and Australia. It has been a staple crop in many cultures, particularly in Africa and Asia (FAO 2020). It is a hardy crop that is well-suited to dry and arid climates and is grown extensively in many parts of the world, including Africa, Asia, and the Americas. Sorghum is a versatile crop that can be used

for a variety of purposes. Sorghum is a crop that is easy to grow and requires relatively little water compared to other cereal crops. It is an important food crop in many parts of the world, particularly in Africa, where it is a staple food for millions of people. Sorghum is also an important crop for small-scale farmers, as it can provide a source of income and help to improve food security in rural communities. Overall, sorghum is a valuable crop that plays an important role in global food and agricultural systems (FAO, 2023).

Sorghum production in Nigeria is a significant contributor to the country's food security and the economy. The country is also the third-largest producer of sorghum globally with an average production of 7.4 million metric tons, after the United States and India (Yahaya *et al.*, 2022).

Agricultural activities remain fundamentally dependent on climatic conditions because climate determines vegetation patterns, crop growth cycles, and the length of productive seasons, which in turn affect yields and the overall supply of food and raw materials. Recent studies indicate that rising temperatures, changes in rainfall patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events are already disrupting traditional crop calendars and reducing productivity in many regions across the globe, particularly in rain-fed farming systems in Africa and other vulnerable areas. For example, climate change has significantly undermined staple crop yields and contributed to heightened food insecurity through prolonged droughts, erratic precipitation, and heat stress in the Sub-Saharan Africa and other tropical regions (Bibi & Rahman, 2023).

Climate smart agriculture (CSA) is an approach to guide the management of agriculture in the era of climate change. CSA aims to provide globally applicable principles on managing agriculture for food security under climate change that could provide a basis for policy support and recommendations by multilateral organizations, such as UN's FAO. The major features of the CSA approach were developed in response to limitations in the international climate policy arena in the understanding of agriculture's role in food security and its potential for capturing synergies between adaptation and mitigation (Tekeste, 2021). The overall aim of CSA is to support efforts from the local to global levels for sustainably use agricultural systems to achieve food security for all people at all times, integrating necessary adaptation and capturing potential mitigation. Three objectives are defined for achieving this aim, sustainably increasing agricultural productivity to support equitable increases in incomes, food security and development; adapting and building resilience to climate change from the farm to national levels; and developing opportunities to reduce GHG emissions from agriculture compared with past trends (FAO, 2023).

Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) is a technique used to improve investment in an agricultural setting to attain sustainable agricultural progress and ensure food availability under climate change. The CSA aims to attain sustainable developments of green economy goals, food availability and conservation of natural assets. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) promotes Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) practices, including sustainable land management, which encourage farmers to adopt sustainable intensification measures such as agroforestry, conservation tillage, residue management, green manuring, and improved water management, ultimately enhancing agricultural productivity (FAO, 2023). The CSA packages enable farmers to use their knowledge and skills more effectively, share information, opt for more efficient pro-environmental technologies, and build stronger associations to effectively negotiate better market prices (Oba *et al.*, 2022).

Since the introduction of CSA has gained widespread recognition and adoption, with many countries and organizations incorporating its principles and practices in to their agricultural development and strategies (FAO, 2023). Climate resilience continues to be at the core of CSA practices, and if African governments do not cooperate, the principle of "leaving no one behind" may be compromised. North Africa has a mean climate resilience score of 63.5, while Southern Africa has a mean score of 43.6. Regional and national differences remain incredibly wide. The negative consequences of climate-related disasters have persisted in West Africa (Usman & Emmanuel, 2023).

Also in the work of Tesfaye (2017) Perception refers to the process of acquisition and understanding of information from one's environment. Farmers have to perceive first that the climate has changed, and

then identify useful adaptations and implement them. For farmers to decide whether or not to adopt a particular measure they must first perceive that climate change has actually occurred. Thus, perception is a necessary prerequisite for adaptation. Therefore to enhance policy towards tackling the challenges that climate change poses to farmers, it is important to have full knowledge of farmers' perception on climate change, potential adaptation measures, and factors affecting adaptation to climate change.

Perception of climate change has been one of the most important factors that enables or hinders the adoption of adaptation strategies among farmers in sub-Saharan Africa. As consumers, farmers evaluate the innovations they receive and practice based on the benefits that it provided to the farmers. Some farmers may tend to adopt adaptation options to reduce the effect of climate change-induced risks such as droughts and floods, while others may prefer to adopt technologies that increase their productivity and income. The innovations may provide these benefits one by one, or multiple benefits may be obtained from a single innovation (Abyiot *et al.*, 2022).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Description of the study area

The study was conducted in the North-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria, with particular emphasis on Katsina, Kano, and Jigawa States. The North-West zone is one of the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria and comprises seven states: Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara. This zone is situated in the Northern part of the country and represents a major agricultural hub characterized by extensive rain-fed farming systems and a predominantly rural population engaged in crop and livestock production (NBS, 2022).

Geographically, the zone lies approximately between latitude 9°N to 14°N and longitude 3°E to 9°E, and it shares international borders with the Republic of Niger to the north. It is bounded by North-Central Nigeria to the south, Northeastern Nigeria to the east, and the Republic of Benin to the west. The region's position within the Sudan and the Guinea savanna agro-ecological zones supports a mixed cropping system dominated by cereal crops such as sorghum, millet, maize, rice, and legumes like cowpea, which are critical to local food security and livelihoods.

The North-West zone experiences a tropical savanna climate, with a marked distinction between the wet and the dry seasons. The region's climate supports the cultivation of sorghum, millet, maize, rice, groundnut, and cowpea, which form the backbone of smallholder farming systems. These crops are adapted to the seasonal rainfall patterns and are essential for household consumption as well as local markets (North-West Nigeria Agricultural Report, 2025).

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Sorghum farmers' in the selected State ADPs (Kano, Katsina and Jigawa) within Northwestern Nigeria were used for the study as the population of the study. Multi-stage sampling technique was also used for the study. The first stage involves purposive selection of three major sorghum producing states in the Northwestern Nigeria which includes Kano, Katsina and Jigawa States. The States selected are mostly agrarian in nature with farming as the main source of income. The second stage involves random selection of agricultural ADP in each selected states. Thirdly, proportionate selection of LGAs from each State, that is, 4, 3 and 2 LGAs from Kano (with a total of 44 LGAs), Katsina (total of 34 LGAs) and Jigawa (27 LGAs) states respectively was randomly selected from each agricultural zone selected making a total of 9 LGAs. The fourth stage entails proportionate random selection of 8, 6 and 4 villages out of the nine sampled LGAs (Ingawa with 11 villages, Mashi 10 villages and Malumfashi with 10 villages for Katsina State. Tsanyawa with 10 villages, Dawakin Tofa with 11 villages, Kura with 10 villages and Bichi with 12 villages for Kano State. While Auyo and Roni with 10 villages each for Jigawa State) with highest production rate were selected which make a total of 18 villages. The reason for these disparities is that states with highest number of LGAs and farmers get more coverage to ensure that more farmers' are captured in the study. The fifth stage is the determination of the sample size from the sample frame, that is, the population of the study; Kano has a total of 3,572,104 farmers, Katsina 1,674,328 and Jigawa 1,375,906 (corresponding to a total of 6,622,338). Based on a 5% margin of error, 50% response

distribution, and 95% confidence level, a sample size of 334 was recommended using Raosoft sample size calculator at 50% margin error, The sixth stage is proportionate distribution of the sample size across the selected three States of 145, 120 and 69 of Kano, Katsina and Jigawa states respectively to generate the sample size of 334. Finally, respondents from each state were proportionately distributed across the selected villages.

$$n = \frac{X}{D} \times N$$

Where:

n = Sample size of farmers selected per village

X = Number of farmers in a village

D = Total number of farmers in all the villages.

N= Recommended sample size for the study by Raosoft sample size calculator.

The proportionate distribution of the sorghum farmers is computed in the following table below

Table 1: Sample size of the Sorghum farmers

S/No.	STATE	L.G.A	Village	Population of farmers	Number of farmers selected	
1.	Katsina	Ingawa	Dara	158	21	
			Mashi	Yandoma	142	19
				Doka	150	19
		Majigiri		126	17	
		Dayi		174	23	
		Karfi		158	21	
		Tsanyawa		120	16	
		Kano	Dawakin Tofa	Kabagiwa	143	19
				Dunbulum	207	27
Alajawa	72			09		
Kura	Gawo		136	18		
	Shinkafi		159	21		
	Bichi		97	13		
3.	Jigawa	Auyo	Dankaza	167	22	
			Yamidi	106	14	
			Gamsarka	123	16	
		Roni	Gimi	158	21	
			Bazara	141	18	
			Total	3	9	18

Source: Reconnaissance survey and Author's computation (2025). List of sorghum farmers' was obtained from KTARDA, KNARDA and JARDA.

Data collection

The study used primary data which was collected using a structured questionnaire. A total of 334 questionnaires were administered to the sampled sorghum farmers by nine (9) trained enumerators. The data collected include information on the socioeconomic variables of the respondents, farmers' perception of CSA practices on sorghum production, among sorghum farmers.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using analytical tools such as descriptive statistics and Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics such as means, percentages, and frequencies it involves tabular presentation of mean, frequency distribution and percentages of the data analyzed. It summarizes and organizes the characteristics of the data collected.

Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance

The Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) is proposed by Maurice G. Kendall and Bernard Babington Smith in 1938. Kendall's coefficient of concordance is a non-parametric statistics that was used in measuring the trend of agreement among several quantitative or semi-quantitative variables that are assessing a set of objects of interest. It measures the association between the perceptions of the raters. The value of the coefficient ranges between zero and one (Hollander et al., 2024).

A type of psychometric response scale (Likert scale) in which respondents specify their level of agreement to test a statement typically in five point was also employed to source the figures that was used in the computation of Kendall's coefficient of concordance which determine the perception of sorghum farmers' on climate smart agricultural practices. The liker scale options are as follows:

- 1= strongly disagree
- 2= disagree
- 3= undecided
- 4= agree
- 5= strongly agree

$$W = \frac{12s}{m^2(n^2 - n)}$$

Where:

W = Kendall's coefficient of concordance

S = Sum of squares of the deviation of each R_i from the mean

R_i = Row sums of ranks

m= Number of raters

n= Number of items being ranked

Kendall's Ratio:

w = 0.10 = weak agreement

w = 0.30 = fairly agreement

w = 0.60 = strong agreement

w = 1.0 = perfect agreement

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics

The result of the socio-economic characteristics of the sorghum farmers as presented in Table 2 shows that the respondents had a minimum age of 27 years and a maximum of 76 years, with a mean age of 50 years. The highest proportions of respondents (25.1%) were within the age bracket of 37–46 years, followed by 24.8% in the 47–56 years range. This indicates that most farmers are middle-aged to older adults, suggesting considerable experience and capacity to engage in labor-intensive sorghum farming activities. The gender distribution shows that 71.9% of respondents were males, while 28.1% were females, indicating that sorghum production is largely male-dominated. The result further reveals that Household size ranged from 2 to 42 persons, with a mean of 16. Most respondents (34.4%) had household sizes of 10–17 persons. Large households are likely to provide sufficient family labor for labor-intensive practices such as mulching and tied ridges. Farming experience ranged from 6 to 54 years, with a mean of 29 years. The educational attainment of the respondents showed that 42.2% had Qur'anic education, 22.2% had secondary education, 19.4% had primary education, and 16.2% had tertiary education. The low formal education level may limit the ability of farmers to adopt complex CSA technologies. Most of the farmers (29.8%) had 25–34 years of experience, indicating substantial knowledge in sorghum

production. Frequency of extension visits showed that 48% of the respondents had zero visits per month, 36.2% had one visit per month, and a small proportion had more frequent visits. The limited extension contact may constrain the adoption of new technologies.

Table 2: Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
27-36	52	15.6
37-46	84	25.1
47-56	83	24.8
57-66	79	23.7
67-76	36	10.8
Mean	50	
Minimum	27	
Maximum	76	
Gender		
Male	240	71.9
Female	94	28.1
Household size		
2-9	99	29.6
10-17	115	34.4
18-25	67	20.1
26-33	35	10.5
34-41	16	4.8
42-49	2	0.6
Minimum	2	
Maximum	42	
Mean	16	
Level of Education		
Primary	65	19.4
Secondary	74	22.2
Tertiary	54	16.2
Quranic	141	42.2
Farming experience		
6-15	57	17.1
16-24	79	23.7
25-34	100	29.8
35-44	71	21.3
45-54	27	8.1
Minimum	6	
Maximum	54	
Mean	29	
Frequency of extension visit		

Once a week	30	9.0
Once in two weeks	23	6.8
Once in a month	121	36.2
Zero visit per month	160	48.0
Total	334	100.0

Source: Field survey, (2025).

Perception of Sorghum Farmers on CSA Practices

The results presented in Table 3 show the perception of sorghum farmers toward the adoption of climate smart agricultural (CSA) practices. Respondents strongly agreed that CSA practices are beneficial for increasing sorghum yield, as indicated by a mean score of 5.03. This finding suggests that farmers clearly recognize the productivity enhancing potential of CSA practices, particularly those that offer visible yield improvements. With respect to the perceptions that say CSA practices reduce climate related risks in sorghum production, CSA practices have significant implications for sorghum production, and sorghum farmers do not use CSA practices due to lack of prior knowledge, respondents agreed with mean scores of 4.45, 4.50, and 4.64, respectively. These results indicate that while farmers acknowledge the role of CSA practices in enhancing resilience to climate variability, inadequate awareness and limited technical knowledge remain major constraints to adoption.

Respondents were undecided on whether CSA practices are effective in reducing soil degradation and whether CSA practices are easy to practice, with mean scores of 3.70 and 3.39, respectively. This uncertainty suggests mixed perceptions regarding the environmental benefits and practical feasibility of some CSA practices, particularly those that are labor intensive or require sustained effort.

Interestingly, respondents disagreed with the statement that CSA practices are much better than traditional farming methods, as reflected by a low mean score of 2.29. This indicates that some farmers still prefer conventional practices, possibly due to familiarity, lower perceived costs, or skepticism about the labor and knowledge requirements of certain CSA technologies.

The overall Kendall's coefficient of concordance of 0.36 indicates a fair level of agreement among respondents regarding the perception statements, suggesting variation in perceptions of CSA practices among sorghum farmers. This implies that there is no strong consensus on CSA adoption in the study area. While there is agreement on the benefits of CSA practices in terms of yield improvement and climate risk reduction, perceptions regarding soil health improvement, ease of practice, and superiority over traditional methods remain diverse. This variation reflects differences in farmers' experience, access to information, and prior exposure to CSA practices.

Table 3: Perception of sorghum farmers' on CSA practices

Perception	Mean score	Scored remarks
CSA practices are beneficial for increasing sorghum yield	5.03	Strongly agreed
Sorghum farmers do not use CSA practices because of no prior knowledge about it	4.64	Agreed
CSA practices reduce climate-related risks in sorghum production	4.45	Agreed
CSA practices are effective in reducing soil degradation in sorghum production	3.70	Undecided
CSA practices have implication on sorghum production	4.50	Agreed
CSA practices are easy to practice	3.39	Undecided
CSA practices are much better than traditional methods	2.29	Disagreed
Kendall Coefficient	0.36	Fair agreement

Source: Field survey, (2025).

Adoption of Climate-Smart Agricultural (CSA) Practices by Sorghum Farmers

The adoption of climate-smart agricultural (CSA) practices by sorghum farmers was assessed across 30 identified CSA practices, as presented in Table 4. Adoption was measured using the frequency and percentage of farmers implementing each practice. The results show that cultural practices such as crop rotation, timely planting, and the use of resistant or improved varieties recorded the highest adoption rate, with 283 respondents (84.7%) implementing them, ranking first among all CSA practices. This high level of adoption suggests that farmers prioritize practices that are relatively familiar, low risk, and compatible with existing farming systems. Crop rotation with legumes and other crops also recorded a high adoption rate, with 278 respondents (83.2%), ranking second, while intercropping sorghum with legumes or other crops ranked third with 268 respondents (80.2%). These results indicate a strong preference for diversified cropping systems among sorghum farmers as a strategy for enhancing soil fertility, reducing production risks, and improving yield stability under climate stress.

Efficient use of inorganic fertilizers, including micro-dosing and site-specific application, was adopted by 259 respondents (77.5%), ranking fourth, while the use of biochar and soil amendments ranked fifth with 252 respondents (75.4%). These results suggest that farmers are increasingly embracing soil fertility management practices that enhance productivity while improving resilience to climate variability.

Moderate adoption levels were observed for practices such as mulching for soil moisture conservation (71.9%), application of organic manure or compost (68.9%), relay and strip cropping (67.4%), and the use of improved, drought-tolerant, or early-maturing sorghum varieties (66.8%). The moderate uptake of these practices suggests that although farmers recognize their agronomic and climate benefits, factors such as labor requirements, availability of organic inputs, and cost constraints may limit broader adoption. Practices such as conservation or minimum tillage (60.8%), community-based seed banks (59.3%), incorporation of crop residues (59.0%), and integrated use of chemical pesticides (58.1%) also recorded moderate adoption levels. This indicates partial acceptance of these practices, possibly due to limited technical knowledge or the need for additional institutional support to ensure effective implementation.

In contrast, low adoption was observed for practices requiring higher technical capacity or institutional support, including access to seasonal weather forecasts and climate advisories (47.6%), use of mobile phones or ICT platforms for CSA information (45.5%), improved post-harvest handling and processing technologies (46.1%), and energy-efficient farm implements (47.3%). These findings suggest that limited access to climate information, digital tools, and financial resources constrain the adoption of more advanced CSA practices.

Table 4: Identified CSA practices adopted by sorghum farmers

CSA practices	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Use of improved/drought-tolerant/early-maturing sorghum seed varieties	223	66.8	
Crop rotation with legumes and other crops	278	83.2	2 ND
Intercropping (sorghum with legumes/other crops);	268	80.2	3 RD
Cover cropping to improve soil health and moisture conservation	170	50.9	
Seed priming and treatment (water soaking, bio-fertilizers, fungicide coating)	208	62.3	
Relay cropping and strip cropping	225	67.4	
Application of organic manure/compost	230	68.9	
Efficient use of inorganic fertilizers (micro-dosing, site-specific application)	259	77.5	4 TH
Use of biochar and soil amendments for improved soil fertility	252	75.4	5 TH
Crop-livestock integration (use of manure and crop	143	42.8	

residues)			
Conservation tillage/minimum tillage practices	203	60.8	
Incorporation of crop residues into the soil	197	59.0	
Mulching to conserve soil moisture and regulate temperature	240	71.9	
Irrigation (drip, sprinkler, solar-powered)	181	54.2	
Water harvesting structures (ponds, small reservoirs, tanks)	217	65.0	
Contour farming, bunds, and terracing to control erosion	180	53.9	
Zai pits and half-moon structures for moisture retention	187	56.0	
Cultural practices (crop rotation, timely planting, resistant varieties)	283	84.7	1 ST
Biological control (use of beneficial insects, natural enemies)	229	68.6	
Safe and efficient use of chemical pesticides (when necessary, integrated with other methods)	194	58.1	
Intercropping crops with trees/shrubs	195	58.4	
Live fencing and shelterbelts to reduce wind erosion and protect crops	201	60.2	
Access to seasonal weather forecasts and climate advisories	159	47.6	
Use of mobile phones/ICT platforms for CSA information dissemination	152	45.5	
Improved storage facilities (e.g., hermetic bags, silos)	203	60.8	
Improved post-harvest handling/processing technologies to reduce losses	154	46.1	
Adoption of solar-powered irrigation and drying technologies	191	57.2	
Use of energy-efficient farm implements to reduce emissions	158	47.3	
Community-based seed banks/cooperatives for timely access to seeds	198	59.3	
Farmer Field Schools (FFS) and participatory training on CSA practices	176	52.7	
Total	6154*	1784.3*	

Source: Field survey, (2025).

***Multiple responses**

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that climate-smart agricultural (CSA) practices hold significant potential for improving sorghum productivity and strengthening farmers' resilience to climate variability in Northwestern Nigeria. Sorghum farmers in study area generally recognize the benefits of CSA practices and exhibit positive perceptions towards their use. However, these favorable perceptions have not fully translated into adequate knowledge and widespread, intensive adoption, indicating the presence of critical institutional, informational, and economic barriers.

REFERENCES

- Abyiot T. M., Belay S. B. & Mintewab B. A. (2022). Effects of perceptions on adoption of climate-smart agriculture innovations. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management* 14(3) 293-311.
- Bibi, F., & Rahman, A. (2023). *An overview of climate change impacts on agriculture and their mitigation strategies*. *Agriculture*, 13(8), 1508. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13081508>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation Statistics (FAOSTAT) (2023). *Statistics of Sorghum production by Countries*.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2020). *Climate-smart agriculture: Managing ecosystems for sustainable livelihoods*. FAO.
- Hollander M., Wolfe D. A., & Chicken E. (2024). *Nonparametric statistical methods* (4th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2022). *Agricultural performance survey report of Nigeria*. NBS. <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng>
- North-West Nigeria Agricultural Report. (2025). *2024 Wet and Dry Season Performance Survey*.
- Oba A. I., Abdullahi H. A., & Jamilu A. A. (2022). Assessment of small-holder rice farmers' adoption level of climate-smart agricultural practices in Kwara State, Nigeria. *FUDMA Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology* 8(1),49-55.
- Tekeste Kifle (2021). Climate-Smart Agricultural (CSA) practices and its implications to food security in Siyadebrina Wayu District, Ethiopia. *African Journal of Agricultural* 17(1), 92-103.
- Tesfaye S. S. (2017). Assessment of Farmers' Perception of Climate Change and Variability and It's Implication for Implementation of Climate-Smart Agricultural Practices. *Journal of Resources Development and Management* 30 (2017), 1-15
- Usman U., & Emmanuel U. H. (2023). Rural farmers' perceptions and adaptations to climate change in sub-Saharan Africa: Does climate-smart agriculture (CSA) matter in Nigeria and Ethiopia? *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 26(3), 613–652. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10018-023-00388-8>
- Yahaya M. A., Shimelis, H., Nebie B., Ojiewo C. O., Danso-Abbeam G. (2022). Sorghum production in Nigeria: opportunities, constraints, and recommendations. *Soil & Plant Science. Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica, Section B*, 72(1), 660-672.